

Assessing the Nature of Russia-China Trade Relations through the Framework of Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)

Shaiza Nazeer¹, Dr. Abdul Basit Khan^{2*}, Dr. Amjad Raza³

¹Visiting Lecturer, Department of Political Science, Government College University, Faisalabad

²Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, Government College University, Faisalabad

³PhD (Political Science), Department of Political Science, Government College University, Faisalabad

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Abdul Basit Khan

Abstract

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) was initially conceived by China to establish transportation corridors to facilitate access to international markets and boost the flow of goods from China to Europe which proved a blessing for many of the regions of the world where China has been involved in trade and investments like Russia, Central Asia, South Asia, African Union, etc. In the backdrop of Russia-Ukraine War and the consequent influx of sanctions over Russia, some emerging economies of the world including Russia and China sensed that the regional cooperation and de-dollarization of the trade is a need of the hour hence they adopted reciprocal means of economic interaction. Besides, it goes without saying that despite China's approach of branding BRI purely as an economic endeavor, the accompanying geopolitical objective of increasing its influence in Eurasia is very much evident. For Russia, therefore, this brings forth both opportunities and challenges. While Russia gets enhanced infrastructure and trade channels, it must secure a balanced partnership with China without letting the latter to affect its own geopolitical influence in Central Asia and Eastern Europe. In the context of the BRI, this study explores the nature of the growing trade relations between China and Russia. In addition to looking into various opportunities for economic cooperation, it seeks to identify barriers to this cooperation caused by trade imbalances, infrastructure limitations, and geopolitical considerations. It finds that the collaboration has so far been beneficial for both of these economic giants however more work is required to truly achieve the results actually desired by the BRI.

Introduction

The BRI was formally established in 2013, paving the way for more commerce and infrastructure development throughout the Eurasian continent (Mendez et al., 2022). A new phase of China's development has begun. China now dominates global trade and has a positive net trade balance with both Europe and the US, just like it did during the Ancient Silk Road. China imports only half of the approximately 1 billion Euros worth of goods that Europe purchases from China each year. China is currently aggressively looking for measures to improve its reputation, bolster its standing abroad, and take the lead in the advancement of global economic ties. China is interested in making sure that its international political and cultural influence grows in proportion to its economic strength, starting from the region of Southeast and Central Asia, since the modern global distribution system was established by other nations and is not yet under Beijing's control (Maçães, 2016).

China first made an international announcement about the "One Belt - One Road" concept in 2013 (Fallon, 2015). Generally speaking, its primary responsibility is to establish transportation corridors to facilitate access to international markets and boost the flow of goods from China to Europe and neighboring regions via Central Asia. Countries like Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and large portions of India, Iran, China, Pakistan, and Russia are all included in this region. The region's geographic center is situated on the borders of China, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan.

The Initiative's name, "Silk Road Economic Belt and the 21st Century Maritime Silk Road," or simply "Belt and Road Initiative" (BRI), was adopted by the National Development and Reform Commission in 2015. Glantz claims that Chinese state officials and business representatives attempt to bring back memories of the prosperous period of trade in ancient China by invoking the image of the Ancient Silk Road (Glantz, 2017). It is not all that shocking when considering the historical parallels, since the effort is commonly referred to as the New Silk Road in several of the participating nations. Although this phrase is no longer used in official Chinese documents and publications, the

previous reduction of OBOR has already established itself as a well-known worldwide brand and is frequently used in scholarly literature.

The security, sociocultural, political, diplomatic, and civilizational facets of many states' and regions' growth are all impacted by OBOR. In the meantime, Chinese officials would rather not highlight the initiative's geopolitical objectives. The International Economic Forum "One Belt - One Road" was held in Beijing in May 2017 and focused on the chances of implementing the plan and new strategy of China's economic expansion. Xi Jinping listed five areas of international cooperation in his speech: free trade, free movement of capital, infrastructure connectivity, political coordination, and enhancement of relations between people (Yamei, 2017).

The OBOR program is unmatched in its scope. 65 nations, or 70% of the world's population, are involved in the initiative's projects. In order to help both China and its partners fulfill their potential for economic development, China suggests working together to implement the OBOR initiative with \$4 trillion in joint investments (Shevtsov, 2017). In addition to China, Pakistan, Kazakhstan, Iran, and Turkey are the most active OBOR backers.

Russia is a key participant in the BRI due to its geographic location. One common example of how it could aid China in trading with Europe is the Northern Sea Route that runs along the Russian Arctic coast. Russia's importance as a vital transit corridor is further increased by the fact that numerous rail and road networks in Central Asia that link China and Europe travel via Russian territory.

A key component of the relationship between China and Russia is energy commerce, and the Power of Siberia pipeline has come to represent this growing cooperation. The pipeline began operating in 2019, bringing natural gas from Russia to China as part of a multi-decade energy agreement that demonstrated the significance of energy in bilateral collaboration. In addition to energy, both nations take use of opportunities in agriculture, technology, and telecommunications. However, their trade relations continue to face some sort of difficulty. Their disparity in economic power is one of the most significant ones. Russia's economy is comparatively smaller

and heavily reliant on oil exports, while China's economy is the second largest in the world. Given that China may dominate the relationship and offer Russia less clout, this could result in potential asymmetry in their connection. Political and economic risks from many BRI projects, particularly in Central Asia, present difficulties for both nations.

In the twenty-first century, China's economic ambitions are focused on Europe via Central Asia. China emerged as the world leader due to its largest population and fastest-growing economy, as seen by metrics like GDP determined by purchasing power parity and the volume of total exports. OBOR grew into a significant initiative that connected nations to the Silk Road Economic Belt (SREB) and was theoretically linked to the Great Silk Road. The Chinese state authorities developed the SREB project's tasks based on the PRC's pre-existing economic priorities in the area: promoting goods, implementing the "soft power" strategy through trade and investment cooperation to allay concerns about Chinese expansion, and fostering a positive public image for commercial projects.

This indicates that China views the SREB as an all-encompassing plan of action to advance its interests worldwide, particularly in its adjacent areas, given that these objectives align with those of its allies. The plan integrates a number of transportation and logistics infrastructure development projects in some strategically significant geographic regions. The Northern Corridor, Central Corridor, and Southern Corridor are the three land routes of SREB that are typically recognized beginning in China, while the initiative includes up to six key lines (Minakir, 2017).

Literature Review

Mendez et al. (2022) highlights how the geopolitical implications of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine have generated new obstacles to the implementation of the China-led BRI. The impact of this battle on the front of financial and basic infrastructure will have immediate

consequences for China's trade throughout Eurasia. China's geopolitical ties, particularly with Western nations, are still being impacted by the case of this war, which raises more questions about China's strategic goals and potential future cooperation with Russian state policies.

A wider analysis of this geopolitical rivalry can be obtained from Dollar et al. (2019) who assert that despite China's approach in branding BRI purely as an economic vision, the accompanying geopolitical vision of increasing its influence in Eurasia is very much evident. For Russia, therefore, this brings forth both opportunities and challenges. While Russia gets enhanced infrastructure and trade channels, it must balance a partnership with China without letting the partnership to diminish its own geopolitical influence in Central Asia and Eastern Europe.

Yu (2020) shows how BRI fundamentally alters the geopolitical order with Russia and China being most affected by this change. With Russia's stance in Eurasia and China's increasing influence via BRI, a balance of power is being achieved. Russia is equally receptive to investments from China but wants to avoid overdependence on China in matters such as energy and security.

In the context of the BRI, the geopolitical ramifications of this collaboration can be considered particularly crucial for understanding the prospects and difficulties in trade relations between China and Russia. Yu (2017) notes that the U.S. and other international players may find it challenging to adapt to new energy security regulations that China can impose, particularly in Eurasia, which presents an opportunity for Russia-China trade in terms of energy commerce and market expansion. This has an impact on Russia, which, as a key Chinese partner, hopes to establish itself as a global energy provider through the BRI, particularly in the fields of oil, gas, and sustainable energy technologies.

Quantitative Trends in Russia-China Trade-Sectoral and Temporal Analysis

Table 1: Sectoral Breakdown of Trade (2023)

Category	Russia's Exports to China	China's Exports to Russia
Energy	47% (crude oil, natural gas, coal)	—

Metals & Minerals	Aluminum, copper, rare earths	–
Agricultural Products	Wheat, soybeans, seafood	–
Machinery & Electronics	–	40% (industrial machinery, electronics)
Vehicles & Auto Parts	–	Electric vehicles, heavy trucks
Consumer Goods	–	Textiles, appliances, smartphones

Source: compiled by the researchers

Table 2: Temporal Trade Volume (2015–2024)

Year	Total Trade Volume (USD Billion)	Key Developments
2015	68	Post-Crimea sanctions; trade contraction
2019	110.9	Power of Siberia pipeline launched
2022	190.3	Surge after Ukraine war; Western sanctions imposed
2023	240.1	Record high; yuan-ruble trade expands
2024	260 (projected)	BRICS expansion; deeper energy and digital cooperation

Source: compiled by the researchers

Impacts of BRI over Russia & Central Asia

i-Habitat Fragmentation & Biological Diversity

Russia and Central Asia's biodiversity will be significantly impacted by the BRI infrastructure growth. Pipelines, railroads, and road development cause migration routes, habitat fragmentation, and faster habitat modification. Due to these new transportation routes, Kazakhstan's saiga antelope population has seen decreased connectivity, particularly on the China-Kazakhstan Road, which passes across steppe habitats and consequently compromises habitat integrity (Teo et al., 2019). Mountain ranges like Tien Shan in Kyrgyzstan and Pamir in Tajikistan are examples of biodiversity hotspots in both countries. Due to the sensitivity of alpine habitat, poor planning of these projects has an impact on snow leopards in these areas (Foggin, 2021).

The Russian ecosystems are equally threatened. Carbon stocks in Russian regions are threatened by fragmented habitat in the boreal woods and wetlands, and a disturbance in the permafrost during building projects might result in methane emissions and harm transportation routes (Larsen, 2021). Due to their high biodiversity

and significance as carbon storage, habitat fragmentation in these areas creates global pathways.

ii-Water Resources and Cross-Border Governance

Aqua pollution is a serious issue all over the globe and Russia is hardly an exception in this regard, particularly in Eastern Russia, where rivers shared with China are threatened by pollution and diversion. Aquatic life and fishing resources in these areas are at risk due to the combined effects of mining, hydropower projects, and industrial corridors (Crude Accountability, 2020). Water insecurity in areas with BRI projects will grow if basin-wide coordination and environmental flow protection are lacking, particularly in light of glacial meltwater reductions brought on by climate change (UNDP, 2022).

iii-Pollution and Public Health

Another important process that directly affects public health is pollution. Runoff, toxic waste, noise pollution, and air pollution are all consequences of building and implementing BRI projects. Industrial hubs linked to logistics

networks within the BRI's purview in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan have seen an increase in the worsening respiratory conditions linked to pollution and dust (Sattar et al., 2022).

According to a research by the Center for Global Sustainability at the University of Maryland, a 1.5°C pathway might reduce PM2.5 concentrations in BRI regions by 35% by 2050, but if a low-carbon transition is not accomplished, this will get worse. Furthermore, a World Bank regional evaluation shows that PM2.5 concentrations in Central Asian cities are six to twelve times higher than WHO standards, mostly during the winter, which has detrimental effects on health. The necessity to make health information publicly available has been highlighted by non-governmental actors as a result of severe health issues brought on by lax regulations and pervasive corruption in these areas.

iv-Carbon Emission & Lock-In Risks

Climate change emissions present a reality with global implications. Projects under the BRI have the potential to either lock nations into high-carbon pathways or facilitate their shift to low-carbon economies (Izimov, 2024).

Role of Private Sector & SMEs in BRI Projects

It is generally believed that, while the BRI has provided access to major financing in infrastructure projects mainly via state banks and policy lenders, local developmental effectiveness critically hinges on ensuring small and medium enterprises and private companies become engaged in contracts, supply chains, and foster capacity-building beyond project lives (World Bank, 2020). As such, country-level participation remains very different, with Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan embarking on some institutional reforms to increasingly incorporate private participation, whereas Russia's focus in Belt and Road projects is mainly on State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) and some projects are jointly completed while subcontracting Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in construction, logistics, and service contracts (Izimov, 2024).

The SME's involvement is based on the financing and procurement structure setup under BRI. A large number of projects under BRI are financed or co-financed by Chinese Policy Banks such as China Development Bank and Export-Import Bank of China, multilateral institutions

such as Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), or developmental banks in participating countries, with procurement systems in most cases favoring EPC (Engineering, Procurement, and Construction) contracts to large contractors and SOEs (Green BRI Center, 2021). The design-build-finance-operate model promotes scale and financial credentials, which small enterprises do not possess, pushing them into support sectors such as material supply, local construction work, transportation, and consulting opportunities in projects under BRI (ITUC, 2021). Wherever countries have transparent competitive procurement mechanism in line with international practices, such as AIIB's guidelines, SME have better access with unbundled contracts, subcontracting requirements, and local content requirements in place (AIIB, 2019). Kazakhstan's reforms in government procurement and Public-Private Partnership (PPP) regimes, assisted by pro-active investment promotion policies, have opened more avenues for local companies to tap into construction and logistics chains in these countries, but capacity building and standards for smaller firms remain a challenge to their effectiveness in participation (World Bank, 2020). The role of capacity and predictability of regulation can have a major impact on SMEs' participation. To make informed decisions in order to bid on projects, SMEs need certainty with regards to licensing matters, environmental regulation, customs rules, and tax treatment. In Uzbekistan, improvements in recent years in streamlining business, customs, and industrial sector regulations have corresponded with a higher level of SME participation in production and logistics related to BRI corridors, despite available credit over a five-year horizon being a major constraint on participation in trade exports in particular (ITUC, 2021).

According to the International Trade Union Confederation (ITUC) report of 2021, access to financing is another structural bottleneck for the region. The challenges for SMEs in Central Asia include high collateral requirements, short-term lending, and a lack of project financing, which affect working capital investment in construction cycles and improving capabilities, making it hard to take advantage of improving investment opportunities in this region. The World Bank

mentioned in its report of 2020 that the credit tools such as supply chain finance, receivable discounting, and performance collateral can mitigate risk and liquidity challenges but need advanced banking systems and enforceable contracts in this region. According to Green BRI Center in 2021, development banks and multilateral lenders have explored blended finance, credit guarantees, and sustainability-linked lending in this respect to attract private involvement but have remained non-uniform in regions because of a lack of awareness and complexity in governance in this respect. Izimov (2024) holds that, in Russia, in addition to other barriers in access to finance among SMEs owing to the international sanctions and a fluctuating exchange rate in this country, financing is heavily reliant on local banks and government support programs, which only favor big players. In this context, private sector engagement with respect to transport projects not only provides extended opportunities in such projects but also the institutional framework of finance, risk sharing, and certainty of law for SMEs become in a better position to undertake such opportunities in their proper context.

Standards and compliance, especially ESHS (Environment, Social, Health, and Security) standards and labor requirements, can either obstruct or be a route for capacity development. Major projects in the BRI are increasingly using ESHS standards compatible with multilateral standards (AIIB, IFC-like standards), but higher compliance costs in terms of paperwork, tracking, and auditing can be a deterrent for SMEs in the AIIB (2019). However, with dedicated capacity building in ESHS standards offered by national governments and project initiators in terms of specialized training, template documents, and shared resources such as common environmental tracking and collective safety education, SMEs can be enabled to conform to the minimum standards at least and remain competitive in the AIIB (2021).

Local content and supply chain integration are considered critical to the developmental role of SMEs participation. Smaller lots from unbundled EPC contracts, feasible local content requirements, and detailing subcontractor rights (payment terms, dispute settlement, performance-linked milestones) can support increased SMEs

participation without sacrificing quality standards (AIIB, 2019). Lessons from Kazakhstan illustrate how focused industrial policies, such as local EPC vendors' approval for local production of materials and components, along with logistics SMEs, can improve local capture in transport corridors (World Bank, 2020). In Uzbekistan, industrial processing zones and special economic zones under the umbrella of BRI transport corridors have facilitated local SME clusters in providing homogeneous inputs, but this can be sustained with continued assistance in standards certification and export assistance (ITUC, 2021). Russia's Far East attests to Chinese investment through state-framework governance, in which Chinese investment engages with joint ventures in agriculture, wood processing, and logistics in Russia's private sector; but in most cases, SMEs lag without special integration tools, with insufficient information on available opportunities (Izimov, 2024).

Digitalization is a cross-cutting enabler. E-procurement systems, digitalized customs, and trade facilitation systems lower transaction costs and information asymmetry, making it easier for SMEs to access opportunities and shortening bid cycles (World Bank, 2020). Digital trade corridors, which integrate logistics tracking systems with electronic documentation and digital payment systems, can better and more transparently integrate SMEs into supply chains (Green BRI Center, 2021). Additionally, SMEs-focused digital capacity-building possibilities (training in cyber safety, digitalized invoicing, and reporting requirements compliance) have been successful in improving performance and reducing contract disputes (AIIB, 2019). However, there are digital divides that necessitate further investment in connection and digital public goods, particularly in distant areas along transportation corridors (ITUC, 2021).

Employment rights, highlighted by ITUC, are inescapable in taking into consideration the negative impact of SME participation in projects on worker rights and safety, leading to maintaining a stable level of worker quality and thus further decreasing project risks (ITUC, 2021). Without ensuring these governance factors in place, general BRI participation may end up being participated in largely by major players only, leaving low-margin and high-risk

undertakings to SME participation, with negligible spill-over effects in terms of other industrial development projects and activities (Izimov, 2024).

Overall, neither the public-private and SMEs engagement in BRI investments in Russia and Central Asia is uniform nor automatic. To state this more explicitly, engagement relies on financial and procurement model alignment with local market fundamentals, support level for standards and financial institutions, and design of supply chain integration schemes. Those countries with a focus on transparent procurement practices, capability-building in a focused manner, and blended financial solutions have shown higher SME level participation; in contrast, countries with covert, bundles-of-deals procurement strategies have not gotten off their mark (World Bank, 2020; AIIB, 2019; Green BRI Center, 2021). With geopolitical and macroeconomic developments in a fluid geo-economic context, incorporating an SMEs-led strategy by unbundling, sharing risk, becoming digital, and focusing on standards will become critical for achieving sustained developmental outcomes from investments in corridors in future (ITUC, 2021; Izimov, 2024).

Comparative Case Studies: Successes and Failures in Joint Infrastructure Development Ventures

The collaborative infrastructure projects under the BRI in Russia and Central Asia are the examples of both the opportunities presented by connectivity and the dangers of poor governance. Through both the successes and failures, it is possible to find the factors which make them possible.

Khorgos Gateway Dry Port (Kazakhstan-China, Success)

The Khorgos Gateway project on the Kazakhstan-China border is considered a success story under the BRI. The project changed a border region into a logistics gateway and improved trade between Europe and Asia. Research scholars have pointed that The project's success could be attributed primarily to Kazakhstan's reforms in customs, investments in multimodal transport infrastructure, and incorporating non-governmental actors into transport operations (Feng, 2024). The Eurasian Research Institute considers Khorgos as an essential logistics and

trade bridge between China and Europe, potentially spilling over into the realm of manufacturing and Small and Medium Enterprises (Eurasian Research Institute, 2020). Some scholars also believe that Khorgos illustrated how global ambitions linked to projects such as the BRI interacted with local governance institutions, creating a hybrid way of governance (TU Delft Repository, 2019).

Khorgos Gateway Dry Port (Kazakhstan-China, Failure)

The Moscow-Kazan high-speed rail project, which was initially designed as a flagship project for Russia and China but is currently being hindered by differences in financing, cost escalations, and political reservations, is a good example of a project where joint ventures have failed due to mismatched financing and governance structures. According to Railway Technology, the project, which aims to achieve a speed of up to 400 km/h, continues to remain stuck due to constant delays and is not yet complete despite being a strategic project (Turner, 2018).

Tajikistan Road and Energy Projects (Mixed Outcome)

In Tajikistan, investments in roads and energy sectors by the BRI have enhanced connectivity and energy production capacity. The World Bank case study on country experience mentions that these investments have assisted in trade facilitation and regional integration (World Bank, 2020). However, debt sustainability and environmental issues are major concerns in this case. Aminjonov & Kholmatov, (2022), support that despite enhancing trade between China and Tajikistan, a challenge in capacity and a possibility of corruption in these investments restrict their contribution to developmental purposes.

Yamal LNG Project (China-Russia, Achievement with Limitations)

The Yamal LNG project in Russia's Arctic, a joint venture between Chinese and Russian companies, is an excellent illustration of teamwork. China acquired liquefied natural gas as a result of the project, which boosted China-Russian energy relations. Zaikov et al. (2024) state that Chinese investments were essential to completing this project, and Russian companies contributed in terms of injecting local experience. However, because they could present problems in

the future, sustainability issues including methane leakage and permafrost disruption were not ignored (Youn & Nazarov, 2022).

Asymmetrical Dynamics in Russia-China Relations: Security and Strategic Autonomy

The strategic collaboration between China and Russia, which is characterized by asymmetrical exchanges that both sides attempt to manage without losing strategic autonomy, is at the center of a shifting Eurasian security and economic framework. In terms of standards, strategic impact, and corridors, China's BRI efforts and Russia's Eurasian regional strategy are comparable. The shared narrative of the second decade of the BRI highlights both strengthening and rebalancing, with China shifting its focus from hard infrastructure investment to risk management and resilience and Russia demanding recognition of its normative beliefs and regional leadership in the post-Soviet arena (China Economic Journal Editorial, 2024).

China possesses an excessive power in defining the boundaries of Eurasian connections due to its economic size and financial backing, whereas Russia's strengths are mostly in established institutions, energy, and non-military security. Research indicates that the relationship between China's BRI and Russia's strategic partnership is becoming more routine, but there are still issues with control over corridors, standards, and the administration of transnational projects related to the BRI (Yilmaz & Liu, 2019).

The justification of this strategic partnership is transactional and has a nested focus, with the Chinese investing in and supplying technology for Russia's energy and logistics sectors while refraining from intervening in such areas where Russia perceives itself as having the most power. China's growth plan is balanced, which take at the same into account the Russian sensitivities with respect to the security liabilities of the Eurasian Economic Union (Yilmaz & Liu, 2019). As a result, these institutional asymmetries are addressed without direct conflict, as demonstrated by the EAEU (Eurasian Economic Union)- BRI interface. Cooperation is motivated by shared benefits in trade facilitation, customs reforms, and regulatory integration at a trade-corridor level, as comparative literature emphasizes, while maintaining autonomy in establishing regulations and creating market

access for each integration initiative in bloc level projects.

Security externalities in economic corridors are controlled by compartmentalization. As noted earlier, Russia's security role, with hard power security, defense industry ties, and basing rights, remains separate from China-led economic integration, which prevents role overlap but enables both to have a role in different realms under strategic autonomy (Yilmaz & Liu, 2019). A Chinese strategy of economic-first engagement lessens direct involvement in role dilemmas but brings soft layers with standards, digital, and financial connectivity, all of which redefine role balances over time in a different way but with a lesser impact on strategic autonomy (China Economic Journal Editorial, 2024; Yilmaz & Liu, 2019).

Strategic hedging can be observed in terms of transport corridors and diversification. Literature shows Russia's support for transport corridors and energy infrastructure in accordance with regional strategic views, meanwhile embracing selective integration of different BRI elements in a bid to tap investment and technology. While China pursues different transport corridor solutions and institutional talk on EAEU to reduce overdependence at a single point and maintain supply chain elasticity. Here, strategic hedging brings an element of redundancy but protects the cooperation from disruptions and change in strategic policies because of interdependence, hence maintaining a delicate balance on enhanced interdependence and state sovereignty in decision-making (Yilmaz & Liu, 2019).

The asymmetries in normative, the governance model, local industry primacy, and sovereignty in regulation—are addressed using the tool of incrementalism. Instead of aggressively pursuing broad convergence, each side focuses on pilot projects or sectoral convergences to establish trust and better understand limits before expansion. Through this tool, autonomy is protected by localizing convergence where commonalities in interests exist and where strategic sensitivities are presently higher, maintaining such divergences. As the agenda in BRI shifts towards sustainability, risk management, and resilience, this incremental tool for selective convergence serves as a

constructive 'anchor' for a stable partnership (China Economic Journal Editorial, 2024).

Yilmaz & Liu quotes that the sustainability of this partnership is contingent upon a 'workable balance' where China will address Russia's demand for status recognition in terms of regional mediation, and Russia will accommodate Chinese leadership in financing and standard diffusion in information and communication technology if decisions over these domains have a given structure of governance. Comparative analysis determines the balance in this case to be political, rather than purely economic, since it corresponds to 'forming a new interstitial space without establishing fixed vertical relationships among actors because these would undermine autonomy.' Hence, the asymmetries would not become an obstacle to but a technique for avoiding entrapment in a collective project by using compartmentalization, redundancy, and selective institutionalization (Yilmaz & Liu, 2019).

Realignments after 2022: Sanctions and the Redirection of Trade, Finance and Energy

The Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 accelerated a radical restructuring of global trade and finance order. The wide-ranging sanctions regime imposed by US, EU, and other countries effectively excluded Russia from being a part of mainstream Western trade and financial systems. However, BRICS's (an alliance of emerging economies including Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) expansion continues to manifest increasingly as a challenge to mainstream global economic systems, largely extending in terms of 'South-South cooperation, exchange rate diversification, and investment in critical infrastructure.' Regarding that development, scholars observe that a 'new trade order with new geographies of trade and financial compression' is emerging, with a 're-layering of global trade and financial relations into concentric circles, parallel transactional architectures, and regionalized commodity systems with a selective form of decoupling and hedging rather than a simple 'bloc thinking' (International Monetary Fund [IMF], 2023; Bank for International Settlements [BIS], 2023).

The sanctions regime, affecting financial, technological, service, and seaborne crude oil price caps, has rerouted Russian exports from

Europe to Asia with increased imports in China and India under reduced prices and intricate maritime routes (International Energy Agency [IEA], 2023; Bruegel, 2022). Additionally, in financial aspects, being shut out from Western payment systems fueled Russia's uptake in using SPFS (Russia's System for Transfer of Financial Messages) and China's CIPS (Cross-Border Interbank Payment System) payment systems, bilateral currencies in settlements, and an increased usage of trade in Chinese renminbi, especially among China and the BRICS nations (BIS, 2023; IMF, 2023).

Sanctions have driven a new reality in Russia's technology and industrial inputs by restricting access to advanced components, dual-use goods and services, thus encouraging import substitution and diversification through non-sanctioning countries (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2023). The macroeconomic impact is mixed: Russia's nominal trade balance indexes have normalized with increased energy exports to Asia, but medium-term productivity and technology transfer are challenged by a lack of capital inflows from the West (IMF, 2023; IEA, 2023). The system-wide impact is the worsening of 'geo-economic fragmentation': each state readjusts exposure to sanctions risk, adds hedged supply chains, and implements redundancy in payment systems, which is a system-wide phenomenon explicitly evident in Russia's experience (IMF, 2023; UN Conference on Trade and Development [UNCTAD], 2023).

BRICS Membership, De-dollarization, and Institutional Limits

After 2022, BRICS membership grew (with Saudi Arabia, UAE, Iran, Egypt, and Ethiopia joining in 2024); this indicated a desire to solidify south-south cooperation in trade, energy, and financial matters (South African Institute of International Affairs [SAIIA], 2024). The rhetoric in BRICS discourse concerns "multipolarity", more trade in local currencies, and establishing the New Development Bank "as a supplement not a replacement for existing multilateral institutions in finance" (New Development Bank [NDB] 2023). As regards implementation, this is a gradual process, with an increase in local currency settlement in individual bilateral trade relationships (primarily in China-Russian trade) but with global

settlement invoiced in dollars and euros, and with issues of convertibility, liquidity, and governance making fast-track de-dollarization would remain less feasible in near future (BIS 2023; IMF 2023). There have been increases in non-dollar lending in the NDB, but operations have suffered due to sanctions over Russian bodies, which have reduced transacts but increased the cost of being compliant—with a seemingly conflicting goal of being in political sync with Russia but being forced to operate within European regulatory spaces in practice (NDB 2023; SAIIA 2024).

Internal BRICS divergences make it difficult to achieve cohesion. For instance, Indian strategic thinking, with membership in the Quadrilateral security initiative and worries about Chinese economic reach, holds back a unified stance on trade and technology; Brazilian thinking emphasizes agricultural trade and climate change funding; Arabian Gulf nations emphasize energy market regulation and investments; and Iranian ambitions center on managing the lifting of sanctions through BRICS channels (SAIIA, 2024). Such views interact but do not overlap completely, which enables a sensible, but not complete, form of cooperation. BRICS will have had its most important influence since 2022 in coordinating energy markets, with Arabian Gulf countries participating in BRICS-modality groups, regional money for bilateral trade, and enhanced political rhetoric in multilateral settings, rather than a full substitution of an existing order in international relations (IEA, 2023).

The New Trade Order: Regionalization and Strategic Hedging

The "New trade order" architectures being erected in the wake of 2022 represent the following three interwoven transformations. First, regionalization, in which supply chains are rebalanced towards geographically and ideologically proximate partners, stressing resilience in the face of sanctions—and observed in Eurasian transport corridors from Russia to China and Central Asia, and in Europe's efforts to diversify Russian energy supplies (IMF, 2023; UNCTAD, 2023). Second, parallel systems, where payment mechanisms, rules of origin, and transaction logistics are diversified—and where SPFS-CIPS connections, regional currencies, and alternative certification regimes are strengthening

partial substitutes less susceptible to centralized control, but with heightened transactional complexity and attendant legal difficulties (BIS, 2023; IMF, 2023). Third, strategic hedging—and where nations manage risk in all directions, nonlinear and non-constituted in alignment with any axiomatic "side," including in BRICS not having abrogated access to Western markets and institutions, under which more established technology and financial capital centers have proven perpetually attractive (SAIIA, 2024).

Energy markets are a case in point. European sanctions and price controls pushed Russian exports of crude oil and refined products to Asia, via "shadow fleet" shipping; a major purchaser of cut-price Russian oil is now India, which exports refined products internationally, confusing conventional trade flows (IEA, 2023; Bruegel, 2022). On the other hand, BRICS membership of Gulf countries adds swing producer power and money to influence price-setting in Asia–Africa trade routes (IEA, 2023; SAIIA, 2024). In financial markets, use of renminbi in Russia–China trade and in specified commodity trade agreements increased, but with very small numbers in global FX turnover and reserve asset structure, mirroring the network benefits of well-established dollar markets and their anchoring effects for established currencies (BIS, 2023; IMF, 2023).

Constraints, Risks, and Likely Trajectories

Amidst these overt shifts, the presence of systemic impediments cannot be ignored. Fragmentation is costly, with countries incurring duplication in regulatory compliance requirements, exposure to currency uncertainty, and lower economies of scale in operations (IMF, 2023; UNCTAD, 2023). Evasion of sanctions leads to side effects of secondary sanctions, making investment less attractive and difficult to facilitate in a transnational setting for companies with operations in different countries (Chatham House, 2023). Decoupling in technology continues in a state of incompleteness, with a Russia-led shift to new suppliers bridging but failing to reach leading performance standards in technology and higher-end service segments in developed countries (Carnegie, 2023).

The most probable course will be a stable hybrid order, where strongly fortified regional blocs and topic-driven blocs share space with a preeminent

core, in which Western-oriented finance systems and standards remain preeminent. BRICS will see a gradual strengthening of convening powers and selective capabilities (local currencies, energy, NDB lending), but will see Russian trade and financial relations funneled through Asia and the Global South because of sanctions. Path dependency, network effects, and institutional depth all point lesser to revolutionary transformation than a gradual evolution, in which redundancy, multilayered systems, and autonomy through diversification will be key imperatives (IMF, 2023; BIS, 2023).

Conclusion

The study reveals that BRI is reshaping world economic and political dynamics very quickly. The projects of BRI are significant nevertheless before approving any project, the respective government should require an environmental and social impact assessment. Instead of focusing on individual projects, the impact evaluation should consider the cumulative effects in these corridors. Contracts that incorporate water, pollution, and biodiversity protection will ensure that the growth of infrastructure does not jeopardize ecological stability and health. Furthermore, when any nation is dependent on state-backed borrowing, vulnerabilities may result. Countries must use a variety of borrowing strategies, including private borrowing, blended finance instruments, and multilateral development banks to reduce this risk. Alongside, risks can be shared in an effort to match them with sustainability through the use of tools like public-private partnerships, green borrowing, and sustainability-linked borrowing. Local financial systems can be enhanced by including local banks in project borrowing.

It goes without saying that the Governments involved in BRI projects must accomplish local content goals and set up procurement procedures in a way that would promote participation of small and medium-sized businesses in BRI projects while ensuring at the same time that they are beneficial to the local community. The infrastructure projects should be used to build local technological know-how and skill sets. Terms of technology transfer, employee training, and research partnerships can be negotiated by the government. By using this strategy, local workers and businesses will be able to develop

their skill sets without having to rely too much on outside firms for future project knowledge. Finally, while taking part in the BRI, countries must be able to retain their strategic independence. Instead of depending on a single contractor or financier, they must diversify their ties and exercise flexibility in their choices. Participating in globalization while having the ability to create a distinct development vision would be the chief aim of every country participating in BRI.

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